

1 **Reuse of Existing Steel Pile Foundations – Greenock**

2 **Creek Bridge, Walkerton, Ontario, Canada**

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9

10 **Abstract**

11 Following a preliminary assessment of bridge replacement/rehabilitation options for the
12 existing Greenock Creek Bridge located near Walkerton in Southwestern Ontario,
13 Canada, the removal of the existing superstructure and the reuse of the existing
14 foundations was selected as the preferred option. The preferred alternative was based
15 on a condition survey of the deck and superstructure, and traffic mobility, economic,
16 sustainability and environmental advantages. The decision is demonstrative of the
17 Ministry of Transportation’s (MTO) commitment to assess new technologies and
18 applications that support its initiatives and operational needs and specifically to
19 encourage the reuse of existing foundations.

20 The existing structure, built in 1971, is a single span structure that carries Hwy 9 over
21 Greenock Creek. The existing abutments are founded on H-Pile foundations that,
22 according to the original construction contract drawings, are approximately 8 m in length
23 and installed at 1:4 and 1:8 batters.

24 The subsurface conditions at the site consist of clayey silt to silt underlain by silty sand
25 with gravel. The groundwater table is at or near the ground surface. The relative density
26 of the subsoils is loose to dense in the surficial 3 to 5 m and becoming very dense
27 below these depths.

28 This paper describes the process of evaluation of the capacity, integrity and durability of
29 the existing steel HP310x79 H-piles. A comprehensive programme was planned,
30 organized and implemented that included exploratory boreholes to verify the subsurface
31 conditions, retrieval of soil samples to determine the corrosivity of the soil and
32 groundwater around the piles in order to assess the degree of corrosivity and
33 geophysical testing including parallel seismic, and borehole magnetometer testing to
34 estimate the embedment lengths of the existing steel piles.

35 The results of this investigation were used to assess if the existing steel pile foundations
36 can carry the new superstructure loads for another 75 years.

37 **Introduction**

38 Following a preliminary assessment of bridge replacement/rehabilitation options for the
39 existing single span Greenock Creek Bridge on Highway 9 near Walkerton in
40 Southwestern Ontario, the removal and replacement of the existing superstructure and
41 the reuse of the existing pile foundations was selected as the preferred option. The
42 preferred alternative was based on a condition survey of the superstructure and traffic
43 mobility, cost effectiveness, sustainability and environmental advantages. The new
44 Ministry of Transportation Guideline for Reuse of Existing Foundations has been applied
45 for this project revolutionizing the approach to assessing the integrity, durability and
46 carrying capacity of the existing piles.

47 According to these guidelines, major items that require assessment for reusing bridge
48 foundations include:

- 49 1. Understanding of the current condition and integrity of the foundation
- 50 2. Determining the load-carrying capacity of the foundation
- 51 3. Estimating the remaining service life of the foundation, and
- 52 4. Evaluating the reused foundation using the guidelines and codes developed for
53 new foundations.

54 A thorough investigation of the subsurface and foundation is needed to complete the
55 assessment.

56 The existing bridge is a 17.7 m long single span structure with the abutments supported
57 on eleven HP310x79 piles battered at 1H:4V to 1H:8V. The piles were designed to be 26
58 feet (7.9 m) long and were driven into very dense silty sand with gravel till. Design load

59 per pile was reported to be 70 tons (630 kN). No pile driving records were available for
60 the existing piles to indicate the as-built length of the piles and corresponding pile
61 capacities.

62

63 The bridge was constructed in 1971 and the bridge is planned for rehabilitation or
64 replacement. An assessment was required to determine whether the existing piles had
65 suffered section loss due to corrosion resulting from road salting operation and to assess
66 the load carrying capacity of the existing piles over an additional service life of 75 years.
67 As discussed in the paper, it was not practical nor cost-effective to expose the abutment
68 piles. Hence an indirect approach was chosen for evaluation of the condition of the
69 existing piles, which included:

- 70 • Drilling a number of boreholes near the existing foundations to collect soil and
71 groundwater samples. Select boreholes were also used to conduct geophysical
72 testing in an attempt to estimate the vertical length of the piles.
- 73 • Conducting resistivity, chloride and pH testing on the samples to assess degree of
74 corrosivity of the soils around the piles.
- 75 • Correlating the degree of corrosivity measured in the soil and groundwater to
76 potential loss of pile section reported in the literature.
- 77 • Determining the structural and geotechnical load carrying capacities of the existing
78 piles by analyses.
- 79 • Estimating the remaining service life of the existing piles

80 The results of this testing programme and assessment are presented in this paper, and
81 indicate that the existing piles may be reused to support the replacement superstructure.

82

83 **Site Description and Geology**

84 Greenock Creek Bridge is located on Highway 9 in the Town of Walkerton in
85 Southwestern Ontario. The existing bridge, constructed in 1971, is a single span structure
86 with a span of 17.7 m. The approach embankments to the bridge are 3 to 4 m high.

87 At the bridge site, the Greenock Creek valley is about 18 m wide and the creek is about
88 1.5 m deep. The existing piles are submerged below the creek water level.

89 The geology of the site indicates that the site is characterized by presence of modern
90 alluvial deposit underlain by glaciofluvial and glaciolacustrine deposits containing silt and
91 clay underlain by sand and gravel and glacial till. Limestone and dolostone bedrock
92 underlies the overburden soils at depth.

93 A photograph of the bridge site is presented in Figure 1.

94

95

Figure 1 – Photograph of Greenock Creek Bridge

96

97 **Site Investigation and Testing**

98 The in situ and laboratory investigation phase consisted of the following components:

- 99
- 100 • Drilling three sampled boreholes at each abutment for a total of six boreholes to
101 define stratigraphy and to collect soil and groundwater samples for testing of
102 corrosivity parameters.
 - 103 • Testing of corrosivity parameters (resistivity, chloride and pH) on a number of soil
104 and groundwater samples to determine degree of corrosivity of the soils and
105 groundwater surrounding the piles.
 - 106 • A set of downhole geophysical tests to estimate the length of the installed piles.
Geophysical testing is required since no pile driving records were available for the

107 existing piles and the length of the installed piles were required to estimate their
108 capacity.

109 The depth of the boreholes drilled ranged from 10.4 to 15.5 m. Four of the boreholes were
110 drilled approximately 1 m offset from the existing piles to facilitate geophysical testing. A
111 50 mm diameter PVC pipe was installed and grouted in four boreholes close to the piles
112 for conducting geophysical tests. Approximate borehole locations and existing pile
113 locations are presented in Figure 2.

114

115 Figure 2 – Borehole Location Plan

116 Selected samples collected from the drilling programme were subjected to moisture
117 content, gradation and Atterberg Limit tests. In addition, 38 soil samples and groundwater
118 and creek water samples were subjected to corrosivity parameter testing including
119 resistivity, electrical conductivity, chloride, sulphate, pH, redox potential and sodium

120 absorption ratio (SAR). Samples taken at close intervals from the top of the existing piles
121 to a depth of 8 m were subjected to corrosivity testing.

122 The downhole geophysical tests conducted at the abutments consisted of the following
123 tests to estimate the pile lengths:

- 124 • Parallel Seismic Test as per ASTM D8381/D8381M-21
- 125 • Borehole Magnetometer Test as per ASTM D6726-01
- 126 • Electromagnetic Test as per ASTM D6726-01
- 127 • Natural Gamma Test as per ASTM D6274-18

128 A photograph of the geophysical test set up is shown in Figure 3.

129

130

131

Figure 3 – Geophysical Testing in progress

132

133 **Soil Stratigraphy**

134 Figure 4 presents a soil profile at the bridge site. The subsurface stratigraphy consisted
135 of asphalt pavement underlain by 3 to 4 m of sand fill approach embankment. The fill is
136 underlain by about 1 m of silty clay to clayey silt which overlies a 3 to 4 m thick layer of
137 compact to very dense sand and gravel. These units are underlain by a very dense layer
138 of sandy silt glacial till. The existing piles were driven into this dense till layer. The
139 groundwater was noted to be at 2.5 to 3.5 m depth coincident with the creek water level.

140

141

142

Figure 4 – Soil Stratigraphy

143

144 **Laboratory Test Results**

145 The results of the geotechnical laboratory results at each soil stratum are summarized in
 146 Table 1.

147 **Table 1. Geotechnical Laboratory Results**

Soil Stratum	Moisture Content (%)	Grain Size Distribution (%)				Atterberg Limits (%)		
		Gravel	Sand	Silt	Clay	PL	LL	PI
Sand & Gravel Fill / Sand Fill	5 to 21	6 to 53	39 to 50	40	4	-	-	-
Silty Clay to Clayey Silt	12 to 53	0	2 to 3	77 to 82	16 to 21	21 to 23	14 to 16	6 to 7
Sand & Gravel	3 to 25	27 to 81	15 to 63	3 to 21		-	-	-
Silty Sand Till	6 to 11	9 to 20	39 to 43	37 to 43	6 to 8	-	-	-

148

149 The results of the corrosivity tests are summarized on Figure 5, which also schematically
 150 shows the relative location of the existing piles. The results were compared to the

151 following guideline, Tables 2a, 2b and 2c, proposed by European Committee for
 152 Standardization EN1993-5, Eurocode 3 – Design of Steel Structures- Part 5, Piling.

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154

155

Figure 5 – Corrosivity Test Result Summary

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157

Table 2a. Effect of Chlorides on Corrosion Potential

Inorganic Chloride Concentration (ug/g)	Degree of Corrosivity
Above 600	Very Corrosive
200 to 600	Moderately Corrosive
50 to 200	Mildly Corrosive
Below 50	Non-Corrosive

158

159

Table 2b. Effect of Resistivity on Corrosion Potential

Soil Resistivity (Ohm.com)	Degree of Corrosivity
Below 500	Very Corrosive
500 to 1,000	Corrosive
1,000 to 1,500	Mildly Corrosive
1,500 to 10,000	Progressively Less Corrosive

160

161

Table 2c. Effect of pH on Corrosion Potential

pH Value	Degree of Corrosivity
Below 5.5	Very Corrosive
5.5 to 6.5	Moderately Corrosive
6.5 to 7.5	Neutral
Above 7.5	None (Alkaline)

162

163 The following conclusion may be drawn from Figure 5:

- 164
- The upper 3 to 4 m thick approach embankment fills are generally corrosive to
- 165 steel piles mainly due to low resistivity and high chloride content. This is largely
- 166 the result of road salting operations over the years.

- 167 • The soils surrounding the upper 1 m of the piles are corrosive in nature due to low
168 resistivity and high chloride content.
- 169 • Below 1 m from the top of the piles, the resistivity and chloride content indicate a
170 mildly corrosive soil environment.
- 171 • The groundwater tested indicates a moderately corrosive environment.
- 172 • pH content of the soils/groundwater tested indicates a non-corrosive (alkaline) and
173 neutral environment.
- 174 • The top of the piles is at the water level. The piles are in submerged condition.
175

176 **Geophysical Testing**

177 Since no pile driving records were available for this site, four different down-hole
178 geophysical testing methodologies were employed in an attempt to estimate the vertical
179 length of the battered piles nearest to Boreholes 22-03, 22-04, 22-05 and 22-06. The
180 following geophysical tests were conducted:

- 181 • Borehole Magnetometer – involves measuring changes in the magnetic field down
182 the borehole. Magnetic field readings were time sampled and referenced to cable-
183 timed cable markers at 0.5 m intervals.
- 184 • Parallel Seismic – relies on the accurate measurement of the transit time for a
185 generated wave to travel from a shot-point on the surface to a receiver (geophone)
186 at sequential depths within the borehole. The velocities at which the waves
187 propagate are then determined from arrival times of the impulse signals.

- 188 • Electromagnetic Measurements (EM) – provide a measurement of the electrical
189 conductivity/resistivity of the surrounding borehole using inductive electromagnetic
190 technique. It also provides an estimate of the magnetic susceptibility.
- 191 • Natural Gamma Ray Logging – this method was used in conjunction with the EM
192 method to distinguish metallic conductors (high conductivity, low gamma) from
193 conductive clay layers in soils.

194

195 An example of downhole geophysical test results are presented in Figure 6 at the east
196 abutment of the bridge. The figure shows the estimated base of pile depths based on the
197 results of the Seismic First Arrival Time, First Derivative of Vertical Magnetic Field,
198 Horizontal Magnetic Field, Apparent Conductivity, Natural Gamma and Magnetic
199 Susceptibility. The magnetic field values (both horizontal and the gradient of the vertical
200 components) for the boreholes show two anomalous zones, one extending from the
201 surface to about 3 m depth, and another centred about 7 m depth. The lower of these two
202 anomalies likely represent the approximate bases of the piles. The gradient of the vertical
203 component showed much clearer peaks than the horizontal component, suggesting that
204 the vertical derivative may be able to delineate the pile extent with greater precision.

205

206 Figure 6 – Geophysical Test Results Indicating Estimated Pile Depth at East Abutment

207 The estimated pile lengths based on the geophysical testing is listed below:

208 West Abutment estimated battered pile length: 6.3 to 6.5 m

209 East Abutment estimated battered pile length: 7.1 to 7.2 m

210 The design pile length was 7.9 m. Out of the four geophysical methods attempted, the
 211 Parallel Seismic and Borehole Magnetometer methods appear to give the clearest
 212 estimation of pile depth for this specific application. The parallel seismic test responds to
 213 vibration induced into the pile while the borehole magnetometer test measures
 214 perturbation in the earth's magnetic field due to the presence of ferrous metal (steel pile).
 215 The natural gamma and electromagnetic conductivity tests are influenced by variations
 216 of clay content, moisture content and metal. The primary reason why natural gamma and
 217 electrical conductivity methods did not respond as well as the other two methods is

218 suspected to be the borehole offset of approximately 1 m from the nearest pile. The
219 borehole conductivity tool measures the bulk conductivity of the material within a distance
220 of 10 to 100 cm with the highest sensitivity within 30 cm. Additionally the contribution of
221 the steel pile to the bulk conductivity can be masked by the variations in ground
222 conductivity.

223

224 **Capacity Assessment of Existing Piles**

225 **Pile Corrosion Assessment**

226 The corrosivity test results reported in Figure 5 indicated that the upper 1 m of the piles
227 are located in a corrosive soil and groundwater environment. The remaining pile is
228 embedded in mildly corrosive environment. Corrosion of steel piles is more likely to occur
229 when they are exposed to corrosive soil and groundwater as well as the presence of
230 moisture and oxygen. Deeper soils have no access to oxygen, resulting in low corrosion
231 potential.

232 The consensus between CALTRANS, NACE, Eurocode and British Standard BS8002:
233 2015 indicate corrosion rates are low to negligible when the piles are submerged. The
234 piles at the Greenock Bridge site are submerged and hence the corrosion potential may
235 be described as low to negligible.

236 However, as indicated above, the corrosivity test results indicate that the upper 1 m of the
237 existing piles appear to be embedded in corrosive soils. Accordingly, a section loss should
238 be applied to the existing piles for assessment of the available pile capacity.

239 The following pile section losses summarized in Table 2 are suggested in various
240 guidelines for potentially corrosive soil and groundwater environment:

241

242 **Table 2: Pile Section Loss in Various Guidelines**

Reference	Section Loss per Side of Pile
CALTRANS	0.025 mm/year
Ottawa LRT Specifications	0.015 mm/year
Eurocode and BS8002-2015	0.015 mm/year

243

244 In light of the fact that only the upper 1 m of the pile may be in corrosive environment and
245 that the Greenock Creek Bridge piles are submerged, a corrosion rate of 0.015 mm/year
246 was selected for estimating section loss of the existing piles over the past and future
247 services lives of the rehabilitated structure.

248

249 **Pile Capacity Assessment**

250 The bridge designer estimated that the proposed rehabilitation consisting of
251 superstructure replacement will result in factored axial reaction of 630 kN per pile at ULS
252 and 480 kN per pile at SLS occurring in the front battered piles. The pile capacity
253 assessment consisted of comparing the demand on the piles with the structural and
254 geotechnical capacity of the piles.

255 *Factored Structural Resistance*

256 The designer also estimated the following factored structural resistance (Table 3) of the
257 HP310x79 piles assuming steel strength of 230 MPa and applying the resistance factors
258 recommended in Canadian Highway Bridge Design Code:

259

260

Table 3: Pile Factored Structural Resistances

Level of Corrosion	Pile Factored Structural Resistance (HP310x79)
No pile corrosion or section loss	1215 kN/pile
35% section loss due to pile corrosion ~65% of pile area	790 kN/pile
65% section loss due to pile corrosion ~35% of pile area	425 kN/pile

261

262 Using a rate of section loss of 0.015 mm/year/face, and a total assumed past and future
263 service life of 130 years for the piles, the section loss is estimated to be 0.015 mm/year x
264 130 years x 2 faces or 3.9 mm of loss due to corrosion. This amounts to 35% corrosion
265 loss on an 11 mm thick pile section and the available corresponding factored pile
266 structural resistance as listed above is 790 kN per pile. This factored pile structural
267 resistance is higher than the load demand on the existing piles of 630 kN ULS and 480

268 kN SLS due to deck replacement work. Accordingly, the remaining factored structural
269 resistance of the existing piles even after 35% section loss is adequate to carry the future
270 bridge loads.

271

272 *Geotechnical Capacity*

273 An assessment of the geotechnical capacity of the existing HP310x79 piles, 6.3 to 7.2 m
274 long as estimated from the geophysical testing, was also carried out. The ultimate
275 geotechnical resistances of the piles in resisting axial compressive load were estimated
276 by adding the ultimate shaft resistance and the ultimate tip resistance as per the Canadian
277 Highway Bridge Design Code. A shaft resistance coefficient (β) ranging from 0.6 to 0.8
278 was used for the compact to dense sand and gravel, and 1.3 to 1.4 for the underlying very
279 dense silty sand till. A method proposed by O'Neil and Reese (1999) was employed to
280 estimate the beta values in the very dense cohesionless till. The unit shaft friction
281 resistances adopted in the calculation were capped at the limiting shaft friction values
282 recommended by the American Petroleum Institute (API) to account for the potential
283 effect of shaft fatigue for piles driven into sands and silts. A toe resistance factor (N_t) of
284 200 for the very dense till was used to estimate the end bearing resistance of the piles.
285 The estimated unit toe resistance in the very dense till was comparable to the observed
286 toe resistance values obtained from a High-Strain Dynamic Testing using a Pile Driving
287 Analyzer (PDA) on H-piles driven into similar cohesionless till. The ultimate shaft capacity
288 of the existing piles was estimated to be about 400 kN while the ultimate end bearing was
289 estimated to be 1600 kN.

290 The assessment indicated that the geotechnical capacity of these short piles driven to
291 refusal in the till is 800 kN at factored ULS and 650 to 700 kN at factored SLS. These
292 geotechnical resistances are also higher than the load demand on the existing piles
293 resulting from the deck replacement work.

294 Based on the above assessment it was concluded that the existing pile foundations and
295 the abutments may be reused for the next life cycle of 75 years with superstructure
296 replacement proposed by the bridge designer.

297

298 **Discussion**

299 While degree of corrosion of piles is best assessed by exposing the piles for visual
300 examination, this was not practical nor cost-effective at the Greenock Bridge site.
301 Accordingly, an indirect approach of measuring the corrosivity parameters in the soils and
302 groundwater surrounding the existing piles and correlating these parameters to existing
303 guidelines for assessment of corrosion of piles was adopted. The corrosivity data
304 indicated that the upper 1 m of the 6 to 7 m long piles is likely surrounded by corrosive
305 environment. The corrosive environment is largely the result of road salting operations.

306 Based on available guidelines for pile section loss in corrosive soils, a section loss of
307 0.015 mm/year per side of pile was selected. The factored structural resistance of each
308 existing pile assuming the above section loss was estimated to be 790 kN which is higher
309 than the maximum axial load demand of 630 kN at ULS on the existing piles due to
310 proposed superstructure replacement. The factored geotechnical resistances of each pile
311 were estimated to be 800 kN at ULS and 650 to 700 kN at SLS and these resistances are

312 higher than the maximum axial load at ULS of 630 kN per pile. Based on this assessment,
313 the Ministry of Transportation of Ontario (MTO) and the designers concluded that the
314 existing abutment pile foundations may be reused for the next life cycle of 75 years with
315 proposed rehabilitation consisting of superstructure replacement. This study also
316 indicated that downhole geophysical test methods consisting of Parallel Seismic Testing
317 and Borehole Magnetometer Testing were deemed the most reliable based on published
318 guidance for the geophysical test used in estimating the length of the existing piles where
319 no pile driving records are available.

320 The reuse of foundations at the Greenock Creek Bridge is expected to result in
321 considerable savings in both construction cost and schedule. The cost savings will be
322 derived from design efficiencies and construction activities related to the construction of
323 new foundations including but not limited to elimination of new piles, wingwall and
324 abutment removal, wingwall and abutment formwork and concreting, and a reduction in
325 shoring and traffic protection. It is estimated that for staged construction, the construction
326 time savings is expected to be 10 to 13 weeks and associated cost saving will be in the
327 order of \$500,000.

328

329 **Conclusions**

330 This paper presents a methodology for assessment of impact of corrosion of the capacity
331 of the steel piles. This methodology allows an assessment of whether the existing
332 foundations can be reused and whether the service life of the existing foundations can be
333 extended.

334 The reuse of bridge foundations is a viable option that can present a significant cost
335 savings in bridge replacement and rehabilitation efforts for aging infrastructure. The
336 potential time savings associated with reuse of foundation can, in turn, reduce mobility
337 impacts, increase the economic viability and sustainability of a project, and reduce
338 environmental impact. The MTO has developed a guideline for reuse of foundations and
339 has developed a decision-making model based on balanced risk management. This
340 guideline has been applied to the rehabilitation of Greenock Creek Bridge near Walkerton,
341 Ontario. The results of this study indicate that the existing pile foundations may be reused
342 at this site for rehabilitation of the bridge.

343 This was a pioneering study of its kind by MTO to assess reuse of foundations for a bridge
344 rehabilitation project. It is anticipated that additional bridge sites where reuse of
345 foundations is practical and cost effective will be undertaken to provide additional
346 confidence in assessment of foundation reuse. MTO is also working on pile load testing
347 and extraction of old steel piles at several sites where a bridge has been demolished to
348 assess corrosion loss and remaining carrying capacity of old piles. The results of these
349 investigations will be reported when completed. These projects are demonstrative of
350 MTO's commitment to assess technologies and applications that support its initiative and
351 operational needs and specifically to encourage the reuse of existing foundations.

352

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